

From Where To Where? Of South Korea Economic Development And Implementation Policies

Dr. Aynur SARAN (ORCID-0000-0002-6343-503x)

**Associate Professor Kürşat Şahin YILDIRIMER(ORCID-0000-0001-
5896-2956)**

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Abstract

South Korea, which was one of the poorest countries in the world during the years in which it was founded, was a country that was exploited by imperialist powers for many years, and their social and cultural life was suppressed. During those years, South Korea was one of the poorest countries in the world. Both World War II and the war that followed in Korea managed its demise.

Both the reason for doing the study and the research question that is connected to it may be found here. In such situation, the question that must be asked is, "How could this nation, whose economy failed in the years it was formed, whose political order was not fixed, and which had a colonial status, finish its growth in a very short period of forty

years, XXI?" How did it rise from the ashes to become the 10th greatest economy in the world in the 19th century, and how did it conduct the "Miracle of the Han River"?

According to this research, South Korea was able to more easily transition from an agricultural culture to an industrial society since the government began "land reform" in 1956. This led to the elimination of big landowners and a comparatively improved distribution of wealth. After the implementation of the five-year plans, an educated and disciplined labor force, an open development model, and the country's success in education, science and technology, research and development, and innovation policies have all been tried to be exposed in the historical process.

Keywords: *South Korea, Developmental state, plans, Applied policies.*

1. Introduction

At the turn of the century, East Asia was home to three of the world's top five most powerful economies. China and Japan, among them, had previously been set up as being in East Asia. East Asia stayed a war-torn, poor area that was unable to fully industrialize until around the middle of the 19th century. XX. XX. Even Japan, which led the way in industrialization at the turn of the century and rose to prominence as a regional modern power, was defeated in World War II. The atomic bombs that were detonated on Hiroshima and Nagasaki at the close of World War II managed the city's complete destruction. Although East Asia was weak and impoverished in the early 1900s, it was of global significance since Great Britain was the greatest part of East Asia at the beginning of the industrial revolution in the late 1700s and early 1800s. Japan was the first example of the modernization of a non-Western civilization. Because East Asia was home to China, which contributed 33 percent of the world's output and was the wealthiest nation on the planet for a century beginning in 500 A.D. following the collapse of the Western Roman Empire, East Asia was a significant part of the global economy. What we conceive of as Western culture was brought to China, Japan, and Korea by way of East Asia. Today, East Asia is a part of the human experience that is shared across the globe. He responded

to the question of how East Asia, which has maintained its existence for thousands of years, can be defined in terms of its history and culture by stating, "It is a country that has been able to use the Chinese writing system for many years, preserved the ideals and values called Confucianism, and inherited the forms of Buddhism, especially specific to this region, in terms of the political structure and laws of the state." culture (Holcombe, 2016). In East Asia, boundaries were not strictly enforced, thus people from diverse cultures were able to interact with one another and share ideas. For instance, the Zen school of Buddhism practiced in Japan originated in India, then traveled to China, and finally made its way to Korea, Vietnam, and Japan. Tea, who is believed to have originated in China 5,000 years ago, became ingrained in the traditions of the countries in East Asia in a manner that was distinct from that of China. Buddhist monks were among those who transported this beverage. There is unmistakable evidence of the impact of Zen Buddhism on traditional Japanese tea rituals (www.asialogy.com 04.04.2022). The People's Republic of China (including Hong Kong, Taiwan, and Singapore), Japan, and Korea have all made significant strides economically in recent times, and this may be considered as an example from global history. South Korea, which is the primary focus of our research, is situated in the southern part of the Korean peninsula, on areas that North Korea once shared with South Korea over the course of their historical unification. The Korean peninsula is a region in East Asia that has a total surface area of 222,154 km² and is found near major powers such as China, Japan, and Russia. 34.-43. It rests between parallels. Manchuria, which is part of China, and Siberia, which is part of Russia, are its northern neighbors, while Japan lies on its eastern side. It is bounded on three sides by water: to the northeast by the Sea of Japan (also known as the Eastern Sea), to the southwest by the Yellow Sea, and to the south by the Korean Pass. On both the south and the west coastlines, there are a variety of sized islands as well as bays. The peninsula is characterized by rugged mountains covered in forest and "foaming streams." The streams get their water supply from the monsoon rains, which begin around the end of June and continue until the beginning of September. The southern part of the peninsula is more amenable to agricultural use, but the northern part of the peninsula has significant mineral deposits. The Korean Peninsula is of geopolitical and strategic significance because, in

addition to being near three influential nations, it serves as a connecting link between Asia and Japan and, as a result, provides Japan with a route leading back into Asia. In this regard, the peninsula has been a battleground for the Mongols, the Chinese, the Japanese, and the Russians for centuries, and in the years that have followed, the United States of America and England have also been featured in this game of geopolitical chess (Lale, 2020). After so many imperialist invasions, the Korean peninsula was finally conquered by Russia and the United States at the conclusion of World War II, after the Japanese surrender. This occupation of the peninsula included both the north and the south of the peninsula. As a direct result of the cold war that raged between these two superpowers, the Korean Peninsula was split in half in the year 1948. Both the "Democratic People's Republic of Korea" in the north, which was ruled by the Soviet Union, and the "Republic of Korea," which was backed by the United States of America, were founded on the peninsula. The north was known as "North Korea." The purpose of our research is to investigate the economic growth of the nation after its democratization and to investigate the means by which it is possible for the nation to rapidly produce cutting-edge technology and to have a voice in international trade by carrying out this period of development in conjunction with the growth of its educational and cultural institutions at the same time. In this context, as the result of a successful strategy and the creation of opportunities from the chaos environment of a country whose political order could not be set up, its economy collapsed, and cultural depression, it is aimed to reveal where it came from by scanning the national and international literature that has been studied. This has been done because of research that has been conducted.

2. History Of The Korean Peninsula And South Korea

- Peninsula History

Even while recorded history in Korea didn't begin until about the MSI century, the country's legendary past really stretches back for older. The first state in Korean history before B.C. It was set up in the year 2333 BC by Tangun, the leader of the Osan tribe

during the thirteenth century BC. It is well known that in the 19th century, Puyi and Kogurya (Korea) tribes collaborated in ruling the region. Later, dynasties known as the Kogurya in the north and the Pekce in the south kept their positions as the dominant power in their respective regions. After driving the Chinese from the Korean Peninsula in 313 AD, the Kogurya Dynasty in the century AD bought total sovereignty and built national unity in the country by putting Kogurya and Baekje under its dominion. Following this era, the Goryeo (Korea) Dynasty (935-1392) and then the Chosan (Joseon) Dynasty (1392-1910) ruled the peninsula respectively (Deik, 2011). For this reason, the Chosan Kingdom was known as the "reclusive kingdom." For many years, the Chosan Kingdom severed its connection with the rest of the world, except for the diplomatic contacts it kept exclusively with China and Japan. However, since it was cut off from worldwide advances, this dynasty was unable to keep up with the naturally growing technology. As a result, it stayed considerably behind in terms of its administrative system, infrastructure, and industry, similar to how a medieval nation would have been (Salmon, 2020). The introverted Chosan Dynasty saw itself as a taxpaying nation (Holcombe, 2016). XIX. At the turn of the century, there was a rise in imperialist expansionism all over the globe because of the development of new systems for quick transportation and technologies of war. Tongzhi in China, Meiji in Japan, and royal restorations in Korea were all taking place during this time. The 1860s marked the beginning of an era of restoration in East Asia. In 1871, Japan founded the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, and as a result, it made the decision to take over its ties with Korea from the Tsushima feudal lord (daimyo), even though Korea refused to acknowledge any emperor other than the Chinese Emperor at the time. The "Kanghwa Treaty" was signed in 1876 between China and Korea. As a result of this agreement, Korea's connections with China were defined, and China acknowledged Korea as an independent nation. The Korean Peninsula was seen as an opening for Japan, a steppingstone toward advancement in Asia, even though Japan has always been involved in warfare. When one considers the nation's history, it becomes abundantly clear that this function has been serving Japan for many, many years. Toyotomi Hideyoshi, the leader of Japan during the 16th century who is credited with preserving the nation's unity, had his sights set on China and intended to do so through

the Korean peninsula. (The China–Japan–Korea Common Histori Text Tri–National Committee, 2010) [The China–Japan–Korea Common Histori Text] In an effort to achieve a consensus on the matter, he sent a team of negotiators to Korea. In this respect, the Koreans responded negatively to the request made by Japan and said that they would support China. In the years that followed, Japan launched an invasion of Korea in 1592, and after unsuccessful peace talks in 1593, the country was seized by Japan for a second time in 1597. (Pratt, 2006). Even though they left the land following Hiyedoshi's death in 1598, the Japanese nonetheless left it in a condition of complete devastation (Eckert et al., 2012). Despite this, the Japanese hid their hopes and ambitions on the fruitful Korean peninsula for a considerable amount of time, waiting for the proper moment and setting. In the year 1876, Japan found itself in a favorable position; the country exerted pressure on Korea to open its ports to trade with certain European states; therefore, Korea, which was unable to withstand the pressure, opened its ports to trade with Japan as well (Deik, 2011). On the other hand, Japan and China have always engaged in a conflict to see who would govern the Korean peninsula. This conflict has always included Korea. In 1884, a group of reformers in Korea staged a coup d'état, and the development of the event brought China and Japan face to face. However, within the framework of the Sino-Japanese Treaty of 1885 (Meyer, 2014), both states withdrew their forces from the country, which resulted in Chinese influence in the country. It was finished (Hwang, 2018) Several years later, in 1894, the Tonghak peasant uprising had its start in the southwestern part of the Korean peninsula. The uprising, which was first motivated by a belief in "Eastern teaching" and was primarily religious in nature, later expanded to encompass demands for the reform of the caste system, and ultimately took on a nationalist tone, which led to the introduction of foreign influences in Korea. started to encompass stopping foreign meddling in the nation and gradually turned its focus on the Joseon Dynasty that was in power at the time. Japan sent its own soldiers, citing its rights arising from the agreement it signed with China in 1885, to suppress the rebellion that was taking place in Korea. The Japanese military force entered Seoul, overthrew the current administration, and formed a new government. This occurred after the Korean state requested military support from China to put down the rebellion. Tensions between Japan

and China erupted once again, leading to the outbreak of war between the two countries, as China declared that it did not acknowledge Japan's presence in Korea or the new government that Japan had created there (Salmon, 2020). XIX. At the end of the 19th century, Japan had the capacity to fight the Chinese hegemony militarily, politically, and culturally. Additionally, Japan had achieved substantial progress on the path to modernization, which meant that it had sophisticated military equipment. When seen from this angle, Japan aspired to become a "great power" and had an imperialistic vision for its future. Even though China had its renowned Northern fleet on the high seas, the war ended in Japan's favor owing to a lack of strategic equipment and poor logistical support. This resulted in Japan being able to achieve victory in the conflict. 1895 saw the signing of the "Shimonoseki" Peace Treaty, during which China formally acknowledged Korea's status as an independent nation (Holcombe, 2019). The current position has produced friction in Japan's ties with Russia, even though it has allowed Japan to grow its dominance in the area. The "Great Korean Empire" was founded by the King of Korea in 1897, and with its establishment, Korea reached the same prestige as China and Japan. Boxer riots broke out in China in 1898, and members of the Boxer organization stormed Beijing in 1900, where they managed the deaths of the German Ambassador and a number of other foreigners. They had a broad notion that western imperialists would tear China apart, but European governments, led by Germany, looked to quell the revolt by bringing the United States of America along with them. Germany oversaw the European states. The insurrection was put down as allied soldiers invaded Beijing and occupied the city. China had to make a sizable indemnity payment as part of the terms of the treaty that it signed with the Allies. During the time that these happenings were taking place, Russia seized Manchuria, which made ties between Russia and Japan even more hostile (Ucarol, 2013). The relationship between Japan and Britain became closer. The crossing of the straits via the Black Sea and arrival at the Aegean and Mediterranean Waters, often known as reaching the warm seas, was Russia's most important and significant historical goal. The Crimean War of 1856, on the other hand, put a damper on their ambitions, and as a result, they refocused their attention on Central Asia and the Far East. By leasing the ports of Devren and Port-Arthur in China in 1898, Russia made it abundantly obvious that it

wanted to link Manchuria to the Trans-Siberian railway and, as a result, to get access to the warm waters from the Far East (Hunter, 2002). Japan made efforts to negotiate an accord with Russia in 1903 and 1904 but received no favorable responses to its proposals. As a result, Japan severed its diplomatic connections with Russia on February 5, 1904, by delivering a message to the Russian government (Apatay, 2002). In the meanwhile, Japan built its fleet in preparation for an eventual encounter with Russia on the coast of Korea (Fuat and Senai, 1321). This was done for the simple reason that Japan's aim was to set up a permanent presence in Korea. In this scenario, it seemed certain that he would begin an onslaught against Russia. However, Japan intended to launch this offensive not on Russian territory but rather on the northern shore of Shemolpo in Korea. This was since this area was covered with ice in February and March, which prevented Russia from making a landing there (Gokdeniz, 1944). In February of 1904, Japan sent a challenge or challenge to Russia (Gokdeniz, 1944). The Japanese fleets split off on February 6, 1904, with one heading for Shemolpo and the other towards Port-Arthur. On February 6-25, 1905, after exceedingly difficult maritime battles waged between Russia and Japan, Japanese soldiers stormed the capital of Manchuria, which was called Mukten, and beat the Russian forces there. As a result, Korea was totally freed of Russians (Apatay, 2002). As a direct consequence of the Russians' acceptance of defeat in the Battle of Coshima on May 28, 1905, they were forced to surrender and make an official request for peace (Bodur, 2013). On September 5, 1905, at Portsmouth, Ohio, the United States, Russia and Japan signed a pact. This conflict inspired and garnered acclaim in nationalist circles throughout Asia, particularly in China, India, and other Asian nations. In addition, the outcomes of this conflict proved that Japan, much like western nations, had imperialist aspirations, most notably concerning XX. During the 19th century, the First World War served as the first steppingstone for both the Russian Revolution and the Asian awakening (Sander, 2013). The conclusion of the war, from Japan's point of view, elevated the country to the rank of "Great State" in international affairs and established Japan as a new force in the region of the Far East (Bodur, 2013). The attempts of Russia to access warm waters from the far east were thwarted, and as a direct consequence of this crushing loss, the Russian Revolution of 1905 took place. Additionally, this revolution served as the

spark that ignited the Bolshevik Revolution of 1917. (Sander, 2015). During this conflict, thousands of Japanese troops were stationed on the Korean Peninsula. As is often the case when a foreign power dominates a nation, this led to the establishment of a repressive political system (Holcomb, 2016). The United States and England were pleased with Japan's triumph after the Portsmouth agreement, and the "1905 Treaty" that was made to ensure Japan's intentions and desires for Korea allowed Japan to keep Korea under its protection. Korea became a Japanese protectorate after this (Hwang, 2018). The organization known as the "General Inspectorate" that Japan formed allowed them to start exerting control over Korea's international affairs and finances. Ultimately, Japan seized the Korean Empire in 1910. (Salmon, 2020). Because of this, the Korean peninsula was subjected to 35 years of colonial control by Japan, during which time its rulers used a technique known as the "iron fist" to ruthlessly oppress and punish the nation. In the collective consciousness of Korean culture, the recollection of this event is still associated with an overwhelming sense of melancholy. The Japanese occupation was so intense that the power provided to the police and gendarmerie with the "Conviction Without Trial" laws put in place in the government regulation in 1910 resulted in arbitrary penalties, and the nation was transformed into a "military camp." The fact that the legislative, administrative, and judicial powers were vested in the hands of the governor-general, who was nominated by Japan, gave the governor a degree of autonomy. As a result, the nation was referred to as a "sovereignty of fear" (Pratt, 2006). Intense integration was undertaken by trying to obliterate the Korean consciousness of the Korean people, who were degraded as being obsolete and immature. This was done to further assimilate the Korean people. At the burial of the last independent Korean Emperor Kojong on March 1, 1919, a group of students opposed the administration by reciting the "Declaration of Independence" that they had written. This was done to make a statement against the government. They were getting started. Because of this, "Independence Day" is celebrated on March 1 on both the American and Mexican sides of the peninsula (Lale, 2020). After 1919, anti-colonial resistance activities grew outside of Korea's boundaries in countries outside of Korea (Salmon, 2020).

- **Transition to the history of South Korea**

There was not the tiniest amount of opposition throughout the years that Japan occupied and annexed the territory they had conquered, and the pressure was centered in the sphere of education and culture. The peninsula adopted Japanese as its official language, banned the use of Korean as a means of communication, mandated the use of Japanese names for people and places, and altered the names of the cities. To avoid the appearance of being anti-Japanese, the publishing licenses of newspapers, periodicals, and books in the country were given to the government, which led to the elimination of the Korean press (Eckert, 2012). In addition, the people's consuming practices have been altered, the consumption culture has been broadened, and the people have been used to living in the western manner and learning about the culture of the west. By 1920, the number of organizations that did not constitute a threat to the administration of the colonial government had increased. These organizations included religious, academic, social, and study groups. In 1922, the administration of the colonial government authorized the publication of Korean newspapers and magazines (Eckert, 2012).

1. Even though there was not another occurrence like the one that occurred in March 1919, the "June 10 Independence Demonstration" was staged on June 10, 1926. This demonstration was planned by student organizations and took place during the burial of King Sunjong, the final king of the Yi Dynasty. However, this resistance continued to be a student movement, much like the events that occurred on March 1. 1929 marked the beginning of the student movement that would go on to become the most significant and influential. The humiliation of Korean female students at the hands of Japanese male students on November 3, 1929, in the city of Gwangju was the last final limit. The resistance, which lasted until March 1930, quickly expanded throughout the nation and took place in a variety of locations. After creating a puppet state in Manchuria in 1931, Japan initiated the Second Sino-Japanese War in 1937. This conflict lasted until 1945. The invasion of China by Japan was detrimental to the United States' interests there. On September 27, 1940, Japan became a member of the "Tripartite Pact" together with

Germany and Italy, which marked the beginning of their involvement in World War II. Being a participant in World War II caused great unease in the United States, but he kept a level head to avoid upsetting Japan. Japan asked that the United States aid China and England, while the United States froze its Japanese receivables in the United States and exercised more control over its commerce with Japan. On December 7, 1941, as a form of retribution, Japan attacked the United States military facilities found at Pearl Harbor in Hawaii. As a result of this occurrence in the United States of America, II. He served in the military throughout World War II (Armaolu, 1999). At the end of 1942, the United States of America secured a victory over the Japanese navy in the Salomon Islands, dealing Japan its first significant loss of the war (Tekeli, 2014). The policies of absorption that Japan has used to Korea II. During the years leading up to the start of World War II, the preparation of all official papers was done in Japanese, and in 1943, education in Korea was totally outlawed (Salmon, 2020). During the war, hundreds of thousands of Koreans were forced to dress up in Japanese uniforms and sent to fight. Meanwhile, Japanese troops sexually assaulted Korean women. It was ultimately destroyed by the Red Army, and its armed forces were abolished, after the initial defeat of Japan, which coincided with the invasion of Soviet Russia into North Korea. In 1942, the Allied troops stop the growth of Japanese territory in the Pacific. In 1943–1944, they secured naval and air dominance. In 1945, Tokyo was attacked from the air, but Japan refused to surrender. To coerce Japan into unconditionally surrendering, the United States of America detonated its first atomic bomb over Hiroshima on August 6, 1945, and its second over Nagasaki on August 9, 1945. On August 10, 1945, Japan publicly acknowledged its loss, and on September 2, 1945, it signed the surrender document. The Korean people saw the defeat of Japan as a step on the path to freedom and independence for their nation from this point on (Salmon, 2020).

- **Korea After 1945**

During the first half of the twentieth century, there were two major wars that raged all over the globe. I. and II., separated by 21 years. War was waged on a global scale, and

whole cultures shared the anguish, grief, and misery that this brought. The goals were quite different. The goal of the conflict during World War I; While it is an unrelenting exchange, II. During World War II, the aim was to get the most possible benefit from the opportunities presented by imperialism, expansionism, and capitalism. These brutal ideas were prevalent throughout World War I, which was fought over a total area of 4 million km² and included 36 nations and a total population of 1.5 billion people. The Second World War was fought across a territory that was 22 million square kilometers in size, and it included the involvement of 61 nations and 1.7 billion people. According to Türkkaya (1969), a total of 42 million individuals lost their lives as a result of both conflicts. The conflicts had a profound impact on the economics of the nations, as well as their social, political, and military systems. Additionally, the demographic structures of the countries were altered. Similar circumstances occurred in Japan, where the national income dropped by fifty percent, the industrial sector suffered a fall, and exports dropped to eight percent, while imports hovered at eighteen percent. The number of cotton spinning machines dropped from 12 million to 2 million, while Japan's coal supplies were cut in half. Japan is an island nation, and its ships were sunk in the conflict (Kennedy, 2002). At a time when it seemed that the world was finally at peace, political and military tension started to build up between the Western Bloc (represented by the United States of America) and the Eastern Bloc (represented by Soviet Russia) as a result of the major powers' divergent points of view. The term "cold war" refers to the period that began in 1947 when the United States of America rejected the Truman Doctrine and continued until 1941, when the Soviet Union was destroyed (Brzezinski, 2000). 1949 was the year that saw the founding of NATO. The "Korean War," which escalated into a fierce struggle on the Korean Peninsula, is considered to have been the most tough time of the Cold War. II. The Korean War, which lasted from 1950 to 1953 and began as a direct result of the choices made by the Allies at the conclusion of World War II, was the first conflict in which the United Nations was directly involved. II. The United States of America during World War II The Ministry of Foreign Affairs devised a scheme in which Korea would be freed from its status as a Japanese colonial and placed under the administration of a "trusteeship system," which would be overseen by four other nations. II is going to be the

primary focus of this approach. During the "Yalta Conference," which was held to discuss the reorganization of European territories following World War II, it was added to the list of topics to be discussed. It was also decided at Yalta to construct a "Guardianship Council" by adopting Russia's side in the conflict and aligning it with the United States, England, and China. While all these things were going on, the United States of America. He wasn't very interested in Korea, but when Russia decided to seize the opportunity on August 9, 1945, when Japan was devastated by the war, Russia entered the peninsula from the north and started the invasion. This caused the United States to become concerned about the possibility that Russia could completely occupy the peninsula. Before his own soldiers arrived in Korea, he extended an invitation to Russia to take part in the invasion. Russia accepted the offer, which was after accepted by the United States on August 10, 1945. Additionally, Russia accepted the line at the 38th parallel and set up two occupation zones. This chaotic circumstance presented the intruders, who intended to shape the result in a way that suited their own interests, with a chance to do so (Hwang, 2018). Specifically, the decision that was made at Yalta on the five-year tutelage produced a significant "intellectual schism." In the north, Russia is a proponent of communism and tutelage, while in the south, the United States is. People who supported communism opposed anticommunism and were opposed to being taught. On the other hand, the Korean people did not believe that the division of the country into north and south was proper and even desired reunification. USA. He advocated the unification of the nation as well as the evacuation of all foreign forces already present there; however, this suggestion was shot down since it was not by the interests of Russia. USA. He managed bringing the Korean problem to the United Nations, which led to the decision being made on November 14, 1947, to reunite Korea and have elections throughout the nation. In contrast, elections were conducted in the south on May 10, 1948, despite Russia's opposition to the idea of holding them in the north. Syngman Rhee was chosen to serve as the nation's first head of state by the newly elected Korean National Assembly. During the time when Japan was occupying South Korea, the conservative and right-wing nationalist leader Syngman Rhee escaped to another country. In July of the same year, the Constitution of Korea was put into effect, and on August 15, 1948, the Republic of

Korea was officially announced. UN. It concluded that the Republic of Korea is the sole legal government for the nation. New republic in 1950, the United States of America and thirty other nations, most notably China (Jeong, 2016).

- **Korean War**

Three and a half months after the adoption of the constitution, elections were held, and the "Supreme Council" was formed. As a result, the Democratic People's Republic of Korea was set up on September 9, 1948, in the north. The constitution that was prepared in North Korea was accepted on February 10, 1948. The position of leader of the government was given to Kim Il-sung, who would go on to become the leader of the state. During the time of the Cold War, the balance of power in the area seemed to be tilted in favor of the Russians. China filled the void that was left after the defeat of Japan, and this circumstance made it possible for communism to grow across Asia. The establishment of the Democratic People's Republic of Korea on the part of the Korean peninsula that is north of the 38th parallel resulted in the acquisition of more land by Russia and the beginning stages of the formation of a new satellite state. To achieve this goal, he was arming North Korea by the prerequisites of the war in preparation for a potential battle. The North Korean army was formed by providing it with artillery, tanks, and planes (Sunalp, 1954), while South Korean morale was placed under strain via the use of propaganda strategies. As a result, a powerful communist bloc was set up in remote Asia, and it assumed the leadership role alongside Russia, which had gained China's support. The scenario was significantly different in the United States of America and South Korea. By 1949, he had completely evacuated his soldiers, leaving behind barely 500 military advisors. Even though a military aid and security pact, ten million dollars of military equipment, and sixty million dollars of help were authorized in 1948, the United States did not make any improvements to the South Korean army since Korea's role in American strategic thinking was not essential. In 1951, South Korea was only able to field a fighting army consisting of ten divisions (Sunalp, 1954). When the 38th Parallel force of North Korea, which consisted of 183,000 men, attacked South Korea on the morning of June

25, 1950, South Korea's forces, which consisted of 13 infantry divisions, 1 armored division, 1 tank regiment, and 150 tactical aircraft, were not in a position to resist this force. South Korea's forces consisted of 13 infantry divisions, 1 armored division, 1 tank regiment, and 150 tactical aircraft. The United Nations and South Korea were both taken aback by the news. The matter was brought up for discussion in the United States Security Council, where it was asked that North Korea pull its soldiers back south of the 38th parallel and quickly call an end to the conflict. However, after a span of only four days, North Korean soldiers conquered Seoul, the capital city of South Korea. They traveled over the Han River and arrived at the line of the Kum River. In response to the urgent request made by the South Korean government, a meeting of the "Security Council" was called, and the command was given for the 7th Fleet to be ready to transfer supplies to South Korea as soon as possible to aid the navy and air force. It was also resolved that South Korea should get aid from all governments that are members of the United Nations to fight the Korean War. According to Yazci (1963), this decision was approved by 53 of the 56 member nations. The defense of South Korea was aided by armed personnel from sixteen other nations, one of which being Turkey. On June 25, 1950, President Truman of the United States selected General Douglas Mac Arthur as the US Far East Commander. This position managed the command and administration of the war. During this period, the United States had already sent its Seventh Fleet to the Taiwan Strait to thwart any potential communist invasion. On September 15, Mac Arthur traveled 27 kilometers in Seoul. He set up a military presence at the far-off port of Incheon. Therefore, the North Korean Forces moved southward toward the United Nations. He was defeated just north of the 38th Parallel when his men and soldiers from Incheon were trapped against one another. On September 28, Seoul was retaken. Following Mac Arthur's triumph, South Korean troops marched north on September 30 and took Pyongyang on October 19, which was the capital of North Korea at the time (Holcombe, 2016). General Mac Arthur paid little attention to Chinese assaults because he was certain that he would prevail in Chinese guerilla warfare. On October 26, Chinese civilian volunteers fired their weapons at South Korean soldiers before retreating and sheltering in tough terrain. China launched its second assault on Seoul on January 4, 1951, using the strategy known as the

"Human Wave." This attack took place on November 27. As a result of his disagreements with the United States, Mac Arthur was fired on April 11th. The "Panmunjeam Armistice Agreement" was finally put to paper on July 27, 1953, after the fighting had been at a standstill since June 1951. (Salman, 2020). At the conclusion of the Korean War, which had lasted for a total of three years, the United States had suffered a loss of 33,000 troops while China had suffered a loss of 800,000 citizens. Korea, on the other hand, appeared as the war's true victor. In this war, which cost the lives of primarily 3 million people of Korea, the country was devastated and devastated, and 10 million people were uprooted from their homeland and disappeared on the peninsula, the nature of which was destroyed. Most significantly, the battle caused a wide chasm to appear between the two different peoples after it was over (Salmon, 2020). In addition, at the conclusion of the war, while President Kim II-sung increased his political power in North Korea, the prestige of the People's Republic of China, which had just been set up, increased. On the other hand, in South Korea, a period of strict military rule that would last for thirty years had begun (Holcombe, 2016). The Treaty of Panmunjeon established the current boundary between North Korea and South Korea at 240 kilometers. 2.4 kilometers on each side of the international boundary. A large territory that serves as a high-security demilitarized zone between the two nations (DMZ). There are now 38,000 American troops deployed in this area (Jeong, 2016 and Holcombe, 2016).

- **Republic Period in South Korea**

system was always having troubles as a result of the constraints on freedoms that were imposed as a result of the National Security Law. By the provisions of the Constitution of 1948, Syngman Rhee was elected as the first president of the First Republic. The President served in both the role of Chief Executive and Chief Executive Officer of the United States. South Korea was democratized as a result of the Korean War, and it became a place where people could exercise their liberties. Indeed, a substantial number of liberties and rights were restored after the war. American politician Syngman Rhee, who later became President of South Korea, had a doctorate in political

science from a university in the United States and held the view that democracy was the best system of governance. However, the president grew autocratic, particularly during the Korean War, and by tampering with the Constitution and the Laws, he was able to win reelection in 1956 and 1960 (Kücük, 2019). These demonstrations were put down with extreme violence, and as a result, hundreds of students lost their lives. Rhee was forced to step down as a consequence of this on April 26, 1960. (Hwang, 2018). II. The order of martial rule was overturned during the Republican era (1960-1963), and with the Constitution of June 15, 1960, it was intended to transition to an order of genuine democracy; Articles for the protection of human rights were added in the constitution (Kücük, 2019). In a coup that took place on May 16, 1961, Major General Park Chung-
hee took control of South Korea (Hwang, 2018). III. On November 16, 1962, the Constitution of the Republic was ratified, the earlier legislative system was done away with, and the previous presidential system was brought back into effect. Up to 1972, Park Chung-hee served in the position of president three times. In 1971, in order to ensure his victory in the election for president, Park Chung-hee disregarded the constitution and dissolved the parliament. IV. The beginning of the Republican era coincided with the adoption of a new constitution on November 21, 1972; Park Chung-hee was granted extraordinary powers; there was a rise in the understanding of anti-communism in the country; banks were nationalized; an attempt was made to establish a capitalist basis in the economy; private enterprise was given opportunities; exports were chosen as the primary target; "finance" was designated as the primary focus; and the phrase "finance" was added to the vocabulary The "caebol," which literally translates to "group of the people," were transformed into family holdings that included many companies. As a result, the workforce was reorganized, and stricter work requirements were implemented. Within this framework, the nation's goal was to transform itself into a producing nation. Park Chung-hee, who ruled Korea for 18 years and was in power at that time, saw economic growth as the cornerstone of the nation's progress and, as a result, the fundamental part of contemporary Korea (Hwang, 2018). The coup that brought hwan to power occurred on December 12th, 1979. The citizens of South Korea were left feeling disheartened as a result of this occurrence since they had hoped for a more democratic

administration. Protests resumed in the nation, rallies with the participation of one hundred thousand South Koreans were held, martial rule was imposed in the nation, parliament and universities were closed, the head of the opposition was detained, and all political parties were shut down (Holcombe, 2019). VI. The beginning of the Republican era occurred when Roh Tae-woo won the elections in a democratic election that was held on December 16, 1987. This victory came about as a direct result of President Park Chun Doo-hwon stepping down in order to avoid jeopardizing the Olympic Games that were scheduled to be held in Seoul in 1988. The Constitution of the Sixth Republic was finally approved on October 27, 1987, marking the beginning of the Sixth Republic. The constitutional framework stipulated that the executive authority would be delegated to the president and the executive arm of government. During his tenure as chairman, Roh Tae-woo expanded South Korea's worldwide presence. Kim Young-sam, who succeeded him as president in the 1993 elections, ordered the earlier presidents Chun Don-hwan and Roh Tae-woo to be tried and condemned for seizing power via coups d'état and then oversaw their executions. Kim Young-sam is the current leader of South Korea. The nation's faith in the administration of justice and responsibility has been bolstered as a result of this process (Hwang, 2018).

1. South Korea's Economic Development Process And Development

Policies

- **Conceptually economic development**

The term "economic development" refers to a growth in the total amount of goods and services produced by an economy (GNP). According to Koklü (1973), the aim of development is not to improve the well-being of a certain class or group but rather to achieve a more equitable distribution of prosperity across society as a whole. In this meaning, progression and growth; It means utilizing the increasing economic opportunities and welfare to solve social problems so that people can reach a better standard of living (Guven, 1995), in this sense, for the realization of development; The

increase in production volume must be continuous, real, and significant, so the society must be able to meet its needs at a more comfortable level compared to the past (Koklü, 1978), to put it more clearly, development; the change in the socio-economic structure to accommodate the needs of the developing society. Producing goods with a greater value-added component is one of the goals of economic growth.

- Improving people's overall quality of life in the society
- Expanding available job possibilities by enhancing the quality of the working environment
- To expand the range of liberties enjoyed within a democratic setting, particularly with regard to the economy and politics, as well as the social and international relationships.
- To be structured in a manner that will cause the least amount of damage to the environment through raising awareness about the need of protecting the environment.

It is possible to classify it as an effort to be in the forefront by establishing objectives on the basis of economic growth in comparison to other societies (Koklü, 1973).

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In this context, economic development can be defined as the process of transforming the production structure of a country to produce high value-added products, fairly distributing the income that results to all segments of society, and ensuring that this equal sharing raises the living standard of the people. In other words, economic development is the process of transforming a country's production structure to produce high value-added products.

A qualitative shift in the economy is referred to as economic development. This change signifies both an increase in production as well as a process of structural change in the institutional and technological framework.

In addition, development consists of the following five components: sustained economic growth; a fundamental shift in production and consumption patterns; technical

advancement; social, institutional, and political modernization; and improvement in the general state of human situations (Adelman and Yeldan, 2000).

In the context of the understanding of "a better life for all" in general, there has been a change in understanding in every decade following the 1950s, when the concept of development emerged, and these changes include the following: in the 1950s, the understanding of "development as economic growth" evolved into the understanding of "development as poverty reduction" in the 1960s, the "structuralist" understanding became dominant in the 1970s, and the "human-centered development" approach brought a neoliberal perspective. In the (UNDP. 1990).

It has become a system-centered development approach that includes economic, humanitarian, and ethical elements, and therefore goes beyond social welfare, where people can reveal their potential, leading to social and economic change, and requiring the system to transform into a structure that ensures the sustainability of development. As a result of these evolution processes that the concept of development has experienced in the last two centuries, development at the point reached today; It has become a system-centered development approach that includes economic, humanitarian, and ethical elements (Turhan, 2020).

- The Idea of Progress and Growth Administration, as well as the Developing Process Throughout History The economy notion of "development," which has obtained diverse contents across different eras in line with the development processes of societies, has not only aspects of the economic sphere, but also elements of the political sphere, the social sphere, and the cultural sphere. Because development is a commodity that only takes economic growth into account, differences in use have appeared throughout the course of history due to infrastructures such as a nation's history, geography, social, economic, and political situation, as well as its human, cultural, and technological characteristics. This is since development is a dynamic process that is always searching for new ways to improve itself. While the idea of development was being explored in the 1950s, the notion of development administration was also being formulated at the same time. Beyond a centrist point of view, it is a process that involves normative and social variables (Turhan,

2020). The primary aim of development management is to accomplish something political, despite the fact that this objective does not include maintaining the integrity of the system or preserving stability. To be more specific, development management recognizes that development is an aim that can be accomplished in a variety of contexts; however, it also acknowledges that each component and each institution share a collective responsibility for accomplishing this objective; accordingly, specific objectives call for specific organizational forms (Heper & Berkman, 1980). Because development includes not only an economic development or an increase in (GNP), but also the development of democracy and the transition from "Agricultural Society to Industrial Society" (Tüylüoğlu, 2004), there have been some changes in the understanding of development management due to the influence of the public management approach in the historical process. This is because development includes not only an economic development or an increase in (GNP). In the 1960s, the government, academic institutions, and private sector companies in the United States began working together, and around the world, particularly in less developed nations, new research institutes were founded (Aslan, 2015). Import-substitution industrialization and development plans that include the state faced challenges because of the Vietnam War and the energy crisis that occurred in the 1970s. The fall of the Berlin Wall and the fall of the Soviet Union in the 1980s, the "market-oriented approach," and consequently, the primary target, which has components such as freedom of interest rates, foreign trade liberalization, and privatization; Neoliberal policies and globalization, which express the understanding of producing as many goods as possible with an understanding that prioritizes quantity rather than quality in production, and putting it into circulation I The free market and equitable access to opportunities have been prioritized heavily under this administration's approach, which stands in striking contrast to socialism. The development of neoliberal policies, which can be summed up as minimizing the intervention of the state in the market, paving the way for privatization (with the theory of deregulation), and removing public spaces from public production areas, has resulted in development management ceding its place to governance and public management. Neoliberalism can be summed up as minimizing the intervention of the state in the market, paving the way for privatization (with the theory

of deregulation), and removing public (Aslan, 2015). In a historical retrospective, the development economy is examined, and it is found that it has been debated by politicians and economists. As a result of this discussion, the development economy has caused many alterations, both in terms of the quality and functioning of the economy. The "industrial revolution" forms the basis of the issue in the context of making a distinction between developed and underdeveloped countries in the contemporary sense. Even though the pursuit of development, growth, and development has existed since the dawn of humanity, the "industrial revolution" is the point of departure for the issue. Considering that the pursuit of development picked up steam during the industrial revolution, it is clear that the development efforts are centered in Europe. However, the accomplishment of this take-off in the United States of America, Asia, and non-European Japan during the process reveals that a different revolution has spread. In this context, development economics appeared in the intellectual vacuum created by the pressure of more or less radical efforts to get rid of the laws set by the world system. This context places emphasis on the fact that development economics appeared in the intellectual vacuum created by pressure. During this time, the state has been in a position to strive to autonomize and centralize the circumstances in the capitalist growth of planning and industry or the national bourgeoisie in the socialist nations that are located in the east and south of the globe (enses, 1996). However, we can see that the idea of development economics is used by some economic historians. However, the concept of development economics is most widely known as the idea that was used by Lilian Knowks, an economic historian, in his book "The Economic Development of the British Overseas Empire," which was published in 1924. Later, Karl Marx contributed to the expanding body of knowledge by introducing the concept of development. He did so by introducing the logic that "the changing economic process changes the social structure, and therefore a change in the economic structure is the cause of the changes in the social structures." The Articles of Association of the League of Nations, which were signed on June 28, 1919, are the first time that the phrase "underdeveloped societies" is used in conjunction with the concept of economic progress. It is said in the agreement that the holy goal of civilization is to ensure the health and prosperity of these peoples. 1947 UN. It has been made clear in the development

plans that the phrase "economic development" refers to something related to the economy, and it has been said that "the ultimate goal of governments in economic development is to increase the welfare level of the entire population." This information can be found in the development plans. Development economics began to emerge as a field in the 1930s, during what was then known as the "World Economic Depression." However, the breakdown of the international economic system between 1939 and 1946, which is now referred to as the "Second World Economic Depression," also contributed to its rise as a field of study. Following the end of World War II, the idea of "Development Economics" started to be reviewed with its economic side, and it quickly became a topic of interest for economists, scientists, and politicians. In this sense, the Second World War is often seen as the moment when the development economy had its official start. The Second World War paved the way for its realization. According to Dulupcu (2002), the "development economy" has supplanted the "colonial economy" as the dominant form of economic activity.

• **The Emergence Of The Concept Of Modern Development After World War**

II. Following the end of World War II, the idea of "development" began to be operationalized, and as a result, it took on a more global scope. The practical and theoretical infrastructure of a new development model has been constructed due to the political, ideological, and economic divergences in global policies. These divergences were caused by globalization. Western Europe serves as both the geographical and chronological launching point for the modernization process, which begins in the eighteenth century. This is the second half of the century that we are now in. Michel Foucault is quoted as saying that the criterion of modernity first appeared as a problem, a demand, a theoretical and technical obstacle, and this demand. He also claims that the western world is moving in the direction of progressive economic, political, social, and cultural rationalization, and therefore differentiation. In other words, the universe should no longer be interpreted in the traditional manner; instead, there should be an emphasis placed on the formation of a new aim science, universal rules, a new political order, a

new economic mindset, and a new social progression. On the other hand, this aim was presented as the idea of "modernization," and it was used in conjunction with the phenomena of change, most notably in connection to the phenomenon of "development." Specifically, modernization; it has been a term that refers to a movement process from traditional to modern and from backwardness to progress. In other words, modernization shows a movement from traditional to contemporary. This pattern of change has also been characterized as "industrialization" according to the ideas of modernization and development that have been developed. Industry is the most fundamental part in development because of the substantial value it adds to the world. The way goods are manufactured, and the living standards of nations are both affected by industrialization, in addition to other aspects such as shifts in thinking. The implementation of an industrialization-based growth strategy should not imply cutting other sectors, but what's the point? However, there are two notable exceptions to this rule: Australia-New Zealand and Canada both began their respective economic developments with agriculture. However, according to Kaynak (2005), industrialization creates the conditions that are most favorable for GDP growth. This is a truth. In this context, economic progress that opens the path for modernization involves new employment possibilities, innovation, research and development studies, democracy, and increased levels of civility for nations. Some economists describe development economics as the study of the growth of capitalist economies from the year 1700 through 1945, including the time known as the Second World War. Other economists limit their study to the period following 1945. Some people have categorized the trend of concentrating on less developed nations following World War II into five distinct breaking periods (Mirakhor and Askari, 2010). To be more specific, the first is the transition of the term from biology to social sciences with the contributions of Adam Smith, and the second is the "Fourth Point Program," which was put forward by US President Truman after 1945 as a new program in order to establish hegemony and to eliminate political instability and backwardness in underdeveloped regions. Both goals were intended to be conducted through the implementation of the program. (Macekura, 2013) fourthly, in the 1990s, in the framework of "human development," the extension of individual liberties, the increase of individual capacities,

and the supply of "holistic" development, After the year 2000, when it was realized that the "growth-inequality-poverty" trio was an inseparable process, efforts were made to bring it to the forefront of discussion by taking into account the effects of savings, trade, foreign capital, foreign aid, and institutions on development. This was the last break in the chain. In this context, With the United Nations' "Millennium Development Goals," many countries have included the issues of ending extreme poverty and hunger, maternal and child health, gender inequality, combating epidemics, and environmental awareness in their post-2000 goals. Many countries have also included the development and aid policies of the UN in their own development and aid policies (Szirmai, 2005).

- **South Korea's Development And Applied Development Policies**

II. Despite the oil shocks and stagflations in industrialized countries, developing countries have shown rapid growth in the period from World War II to the present. One of these countries, South Korea, with its performance since the beginning of the 1960s, has achieved the industrial revolution in a brief period of 40 years for the states, which could be realized in 150 years by the UK, 100 years by the USA, and 75 years by Japan.

While it was a poor and crowded country with a GDP per capita of \$ 91 and a population of 25.7 million in 1961, today it is the 10th largest economy in the world with a GDP of \$ 35,200 and an economy of \$ 1,823,852 million according to the IMF 2021 report. It has been the 4th largest economy of Turkey (Değirmenci, 2019). It has been seen that the policies followed in the industrialization-education-technology spiral together with the macroeconomic policies pursued on the high economic performance of South Korea, which is expressed by the phrase "The Miracle of the Han River". This economic development, which developed between 1960 and 2010, was expressed as a miracle, a "third generation industrial revolution" that was admired all over the world. South Korea, which entered the literature as a country that increased its per capita income from only \$944 in 1960 to \$22,086 in 2010 according to buying power parity , sets an example for underdeveloped countries (Çetin and Karadaş, 2018).).

While it was a backward and underdeveloped country in the 1950s, it developed its non-traditional industries in the 1960s and became a country that exports based on labor-intensive business lines. In the following years, it has become the world's largest producer and exporter in the iron-steel, machinery, electronics, petroleum-chemistry, metallurgy and shipbuilding sectors, and a world giant in capital and technology-intensive production and export. Esiyok, 2010).

With the annexation of Korea by Japan in 1910, the Korean peninsula experienced a 35-year colonial period, and the Korean people were left in great poverty (Doğan, 2007). It has been an object of the ambitions of China and Japan until the 19th century, and then of the imperialist powers. In the colonial years XIX. The Japanese colonial administration and Japanese immigrants helped the most from the development movements and technological developments that began at the end of the century. In this context, 94% of the industrial assets between 1910-1945 belonged to Japanese immigrants. Because Korean entrepreneurs did not have a capital accumulation that could compete with Japanese entrepreneurs at that time, and the Korean economy was mainly agricultural until that time (Atay, 2015).

Since the 1930s, Japan has focused on the production of industrial products in addition to agriculture in Korea and started industrial investments in these regions to use the high-reserve underground resources in the north of Korea (Bakkal et al., 2012). Japan XIX. By following the global technological developments in the world in the 21st century, it has focused on closing the technological gap with developed countries. For this purpose, it enabled them to industrialize by developing their technologies on the one hand, and to get rid of the "middle income" trap they lived in, and thus to enter a sustainable growth process. In 1930, Japanese economist Kaname Akamatsu described an economic model he called the "Flying Goose Model". In this model, there is a leading country and countries that follow and imitate it. The countries following that country would learn about the structural changes implemented by the leading country by going through the same stages. The model is designed as a transition from labor-intensive economies to capital-intensive economies (Tiryakioğlu, 2015). "Flying Goose Model"; It

expresses the development of late developing countries by teaching the industrial and technological knowledge they learned from the leading countries by using the imitation method to the countries that follow them. In this context, Hong Kong, Taiwan, Singapore and South Korea, which followed the industrialization of Japan, accelerated their development with this model. South Korea has also succeeded in overcoming its crises with the right policies it has implemented (Kavurmacı, 2020).

In the Flying Goose model, While the first stage of the development process is the import of industrial goods and the export of consumer goods, that is, raw materials, in the second stage, imported products are started to be produced with the "import substitution system" in the first stage. learning method begins. In the third stage, while ready-to-use consumer goods are exported, industrial products are started to be produced domestically and the imports of these products are reduced. In the fourth stage, both capital goods are produced domestically, and a development is achieved in an exportable manner at equal levels with developed countries (Kavurmacı, 2020).

South Korea put this model into practice, which Japan laid the foundations of in the 1960s, and developed its industry with planned industrialization programs and export-oriented government supports. After 1980, R&D studies were increased, and after 1997, the country's ICT (Information and Communication Technologies) sector gained a targeted structure. Today, South Korea has a solid infrastructure, high technology and especially important world companies thanks to the export and technology-oriented economic development model it has implemented and has started to export culture in parallel with political democratization (Kavurmacı, 2020).

The Korean War, covering the years 1950-1953, was a disaster for South Korea. Between 1953 and 1961, the main economic policy of South Korea, which tried to save its economy with the help of the USA, was primarily "import substitution economic policy" and its orientation to public expenditures on education. When General Park came to power in a coup in 1961, South Korea was far behind North Korea in terms of both GDP and industrial production. General Park became obsessed with capturing and even surpassing North Korea, adopting the country-wide "export" the strategy of "building a

nation” was put forward, the threat of the USA, which provided foreign aid to the country in the same period, to cut off aid, and the anti- dumping practices of South Korea's export goods and import bans since the 1970s, triggered South Korea's goal of an independent development. In this context, obtaining the foreign exchange revenues needed by the economy through exports was accepted throughout the country (Weiss and Hobson, 1999). Thus, any class resistance was prevented by using a supra-class rhetoric. During this period, companies were provided with investment support, credit opportunities were increased, and well-managed companies were rewarded with negative interest. In 1962, the "Economic Planning Board" was set up, five-year development plans were made, and "export and productivity" targets were decided (Çakmak, 2016), seven "Five-Year Development Plans" covering the years 1962-1997 were prepared and implemented, thus, South Korea's economy was expanded. The “Developmentalist State Model” was launched.

i . During the BYP (1962-1966) period, banks were nationalized, public or semi-public offices such as "Kotra" were set up to help the private sector, "chaebol", which were large Korean companies, began to be created, import-substituting industrialization, an export-based policy in labor-intensive sectors. was put into effect. In these developmental policies of South Korea, the "Land Reform" made between 1948 and 1952 was effective in the state's gaining relative autonomy in these developmental policies, and as a result of this reform, 70% of the land was distributed to landless peasants and peasant revolts that could occur during the industrialization movements between 1960 and 1970 were prevented (Çakmak , 2015). Since this period was a period in which "state-controlled development policies" were implemented, the state aimed to quickly end the country's poverty, so the first target was to encourage exports with government support.

II. ByP (1967-1971) import-substitution approach was introduced, exports were increased in labor-intensive sectors to complete the unfinished projects from the first period, an active exchange rate policy was followed, meanwhile, the modernization of rural areas (Saemaul Undong), the development of forestry and fisheries, the development of grain products Being self-sufficient and increasing the employment rate depending on

the increase in technology and productivity were the important topics of this plan (Demir, 2012).

III . BYP (1972-1976) This period was a period in which heavy industry and chemical industry were encouraged and it was aimed to create an export-oriented structure especially in iron-steel, transportation vehicles and machinery, shipbuilding, petro-chemistry and electrical household appliances. Meanwhile, a campaign called a community movement (Seamaul Undong) was launched to keep the national unity alive (Park, 2009). In addition, state supports to rural areas have largely closed the gap between rural and urban development (Kavurmacı, 2020). During this period, the slowdown in the growth rates experienced in the USA and Japan in 1971-1972 also affected South Korea, and large companies were damaged due to the 10% added tax imposed by the USA on the products imported as export input, and the depreciation of the W against the dollar resulted in the loss of debts. The growth rate decreased to 4.9% in 1972 .

IV. ByP (1977-1981) The policies of this period were to increase employment, develop workforce, improve the environment, increase investments in science and technology, regulate economy management and institutions (Okan, 1998).

V. BYP (1982-1986) After the 1970s, the South Korean economy overheated, and therefore, an "inflationary" period was entered due to the rapid expansion in exports and increase in demand, which led to the formation of negative real interest rates. The appreciation of the won decreased its competitiveness and slowed down exports. To get rid of these problems, price controls were loosened, restrictions on imports were lifted, and tax reform was started within the scope of the government's "stability policies" (Çakmak, 2016). The shares held by the public owned by the banks were sold to the private sector, advanced technology products were produced, R&D was left to the private sector, and public R&D institutions assumed the relationship between universities and businesses (Bakkal et al. 2012). As a result of the policies implemented, in 1986, the foreign trade current account and balance of payments surplus emerged thanks to the decrease in inflation rates, weak dollar exchange rate and low interest rates, and South

Korea achieved a growth rate of 11%. While the export of the high-tech products produced is the main target, it ranked second in the list of export items (Kavurmacı, 2020).

VI. BYP (1987-1991) In the planning of the period, the targets were decided in the direction of "a developed economy" and "social welfare and balanced growth", and "removal of import restrictions and liberalization of imports". In this context, South Korea, which started democratization with the free elections held in 1987, revised its sixth development plan in 1988, and reforms were conducted including issues such as land ownership, financial transactions, economic power of large holdings called chaebol, and worker-employer relations (Gönel, 2014).

VII. BYP (1992-1996) This planning, announced by the then President Roh , was canceled by Kim Young-sam, who was elected president in 1993, and was replaced by the "New Economy BMP" covering the years 1993-1997. In this planning, industrialization and technological progress were decided as the basic policy, and it was aimed to increase job opportunities, bring export products to a level that could compete with the world, and expand the economy. Thus, it was decided to develop the country in advanced technology areas by creating an "advanced industrial economy" until 2000, to reduce the state's interventions in the economy, to strengthen the private sector, to spread the industry all over the country and to supply industrial-state cooperation in this regard (TMMOB, 2007).

In this context, financial liberalization, technological development and globalization have become the primary goals (Çakmak, 2016). Although the "Asian economic crisis" experienced in 1997 caused a problem in the South Korean economy, it caused it to turn into an information technology-based structure (Çakmak, 2016).

3. Policies Applied In Development

Industrial Policies

Industrial policies are a concept that refer to the promotion of the development of predetermined sectors. Since these sectors are the primary tool of the developmental state, industrial policies encompass the methods of selecting and developing sectors that will increase the economic welfare of the nation over the long term. Within this framework, several industries have been given the opportunity to use resources like international trade subsidies, licenses, capital and loan allocations. South Korean "selected industry" strategies have had the main aim of "replacing low value-added industries with high value-added goods with high technology content," and this has been their major focus. In this context, policy measures such as aid with foreign currency, tax relief, and low-interest loans have been put into effect to modernize the structure of the sector and boost production. These tools were put into operation to: A restrictive foreign trade policy was established in the domestic market at the same time as limitations were put on foreign direct investments. Additionally, the state played an active and key role in resource allocation (Schmitz, 1996).

TABLE 1: Korea's Industrial Policy Objectives

Industrial Structure Deepening	Encouragement of Domestic Input Use	Direct Investment Strategy	Increasing Technology Efforts	Encouragement of Large Domestic Enterprises
Strong push to capital, skills and technology intensive sectors, especially heavy intermediate and capital goods	Strict rules for the use of domestic inputs, creation of support industries, protection of domestic suppliers, subcontracting incentives	Rejection of FDI, encouragement of joint ventures and licensing agreements unless necessary for access or export of technology	Ambitious domestic R&D in advanced industry, intensive investments in technology infrastructure, targeting strategic technologies	A continuous effort to create huge private sector conglomerates that will lead heavy industries and create export brands

Source: Sanjaya Lall (2009)

As can be seen in Table 1, license agreements were prioritized over foreign investments in South Korea's process of buying technology. Additionally, investments were made in technology infrastructures in conjunction with R&D activities, and the development of strategic technologies was a primary goal. Priority was given to activities aimed at the domestic market, and attempts were made to set up holdings that might prove brands in international trade. Within this framework, human resources have been the most fundamental part of the development process, and it has been recommended that these resources be used in the most effective manner possible. The level of technological ability had by the labor force has improved, and both the number of engineers and the proportion of students enrolled in universities have gone up (Lall, 2009).

TABLE 2: Main Features of Industrialization Strategy in Korea

1960s	1970s
<p>Exports in light industries (labor intensive industries) were expanded.</p> <p>Institutions for industrialization were created (MOST of Science and Technology), Korea The Institute of Science and Technology (KIST) and the Korea Scientific and Technology Information Center are among these institutions.</p> <p>Subsidized loan allocations were made.</p> <p>Exports were subsidized.</p> <p>Import protection was applied.</p> <p>The manufacturing goods industry was supported.</p>	<p>“Chemistry and Heavy Industry Development Plan” was put into practice in 1973. In this context, the petro-chemistry, steel, shipbuilding, electronics and machinery industries and non-ferrous metals sectors were decided as priority sectors.</p> <p>Weight shifted from capital imports to technology imports.</p> <p>The competitiveness of export-oriented industries has been increased.</p> <p>Import protection was applied.</p> <p>Exports were subsidized.</p> <p>Subsidized loan allocations were made.</p> <p>Export was targeted.</p> <p>Investments were encouraged through regulations in taxes.</p> <p>Small and medium-sized facilities were encouraged.</p>
1980s	1990s and later
<p>The industrial structure was brought to a more advanced and balanced level.</p> <p>Firms needed restructuring.</p> <p>The phase of liberalization of imports has begun.</p>	<p>Adaptation of the industrial structure to the new order and technological innovations were encouraged.</p> <p>The information network has been improved.</p>

The government's influence on loan allocations continued. R&D investments were encouraged. Restrictions on direct investments (FDI) were relaxed. Technology-intensive industries were encouraged. Human resources have been developed. The Information Industry was promoted.	Development policies were put into effect under the leadership of the private sector. After the 1997 crisis, the chaebols were restructured. Effective use of human and other resources was encouraged. There was liberalization in the financial sector.
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Source : Based on Kemal Pak & Ergün Türkcan (2000), Hainder Khan (2008) and John Weiss (2005).

4. Foreign Trade Policies

South Korea has kept sector abilities above the domestic demand to direct companies toward exporting, thereby creating an opportunity for domestic competition without opening the domestic market to competition from foreign markets. The South Korean government has adopted the slogan "export first" in the context of foreign trade. It did this by tying the advantage of large profits in the home market to the need of exporting, which resulted in the creation of a competitive industrial system. Through monthly export meetings, the state informed both commercial and public organizations as well as said their export aims; export strategies were characterized as "pragmatic, quick, and adaptable." Through its branches in 80 different countries all over the globe, the Korea Trade Development Agency (KOTRA) was able to offer the local importer enterprises with the information that they need. Since 1998, South Korea has been a nation that has a surplus in its foreign trade because to the policies that have been put into place about trade with other countries, except for 2008. (TC Ministry of Economy, 2017).

5. Science and Technology Policies

In the 1960s, in order to ensure the welfare of the people in South Korea, whose national product was based on agriculture and whose per capita income was very low, the

primary goal was to increase the share of the industrial sector in the economy; however, in order to achieve this goal, it was necessary to transfer technology to the country. In order to achieve this goal, it was necessary to increase the share of the industrial sector in the economy; however, in order to achieve this goal, it was necessary to increase the share of the industrial In order to transfer technology, there were choices to either bring in direct investment from overseas, pay licensing fees to foreign corporations, or take out long-term loans in order to acquire capital goods from other countries. Between the years 1962 and 1981, South Korea was mired in long-term debt. As a result, the establishment of a planned infrastructure for science and technology was one of the goals, along with the control of the transfer of technology from the center, the delegation of tasks to large corporations (chaebol), and the advancement of traditional technologies through research and development. First, the technologies that were created in more developed nations were exported, then these exported technologies were learnt, and finally, the technologies that were learned started to be duplicated at a higher level. The stages of "creative imitation," "reverse engineering," and "imitation as it is" made up the technical learning process in this order. "Imitation as it is" came first.

TABLE 3: Stages of Development of Science and Technology Policies in Korea

1960s	1970s
Science and Technology education started Science and Technology infrastructure was set up, institutional and legal arrangements were made. Import of advanced technologies has been eased.	Science and technology education was expanded in priority areas. Institutional adaptation mechanisms of imported technologies were improved. Research that can be applied to industry needs was encouraged, the technological research and development ability of the industry was strengthened, the law to support technological development and the law to support engineering services were enacted.
1980s	1990s and later
Top engineers and scientists were trained or developed. National R&D projects were conducted effectively.	National R&D projects were reviewed and organized.

The development of industrial technologies was encouraged. Efforts to set up a national innovation system were intensified.	The demand-oriented technology development system was strengthened, and technology imports were liberalized. R&D systems and information network were internationalized. Science and Technology infrastructure was re-established, preparations for the information society were started.
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Source : It was created by us based on Kemal Pak & Ergün *Türkcan* (2000), Hainder Khan (2008).

The state supplied R&D and engineering support to local companies to support the upgrading of science and technology skills , so local companies were able to use the skills and innovation flow in world technologies. Today, South Korea aims to become the 7th power of the world in new generation products and technologies with its long-term plan called “Vision 2025” (Eşiyok, 2010).

6. Education R&D and Innovation Policies

The education level and the number of skilled workers in a nation are related to its economic growth. The growth of the miracle that South Korea has reached since the 1960s is in large part due to the deep-seated changes in education as well as the consistent policies that have been in place. South Korea's education policies include: allocating a high share of the general budget to education; ensuring the professional development of teachers; establishing world-class research universities that will increase the quality of higher education; achieving great goals in the field of science and technology; improving English education; making effective use of information technologies in education; educating gifted children and training teachers to take part in this education; and educating gifted children and training teachers to take part in this education and training. Economists believe that South Korea's success may be attributed to the country's policies

as well as its investments in education, research and development, and innovation. After 1980, the government shifted its focus from an industrial strategy to a technology strategy and assigned the private sector to R&D studies. As a result, product development and the sales and marketing of the developed product became easier, and the private sector gained a competitive structure (Arslanhan and Kurtsal, 2010). Additionally, investments were made in R&D and technology. The number of patents, which was at 219 in the year 1960, increased to 20,678 by the year 2021. (WIPO, 2021). Throughout this procedure, a strong focus was focused on developing policies that would enhance R&D education. In this light, South Korea was able to effectively complete the phases of imitation during the years 1960–1970, transformation during the years 1980, and invention during the years 1990. The Chaebols that control a substantial part of the South Korean economy, such as Hyundai, Samsung, LG, and SK, combined to spend 4.731 billion Korean Won on research and development in the year 2000. In this light, it is possible to assert that there have been implementations of R&D and innovation policies following in the footsteps of South Korea's growth narrative.

7. Conclusion

After the conclusion of World War II, Japan's control over South Korea ended, and the country went on to enjoy a period of immense success and development from the time it gained its independence in 1948 until the 2000s. Within the framework of the five-year development plans that it put into reality, it began manufacturing high-value-added and innovative technological items in 1960. This was conducted via the implementation of a selective and export-based industrialization program. It has achieved its development by placing a strong emphasis on research and development as well as innovation to narrow the gap brought about by macroeconomic imbalances, financial indicators, and technical superiorities and to take part in international competition. It has implemented its policies in a stable and harmonious way, showing that an underdeveloped economy can supply both capital accumulation and technological development within the framework of a

development paradigm that is based on planning. This is since education, economy, and technology policies are the prerequisites for being a developed country.

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